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Review Article

PROCESS ANALYTICAL TECHNOLOGY**E Naga Deepthi and Madduri Vamshi Yadav**Pharmaceutical Analysis, Dr K V Subba Reddy Institute of Pharmacy,
Opp. Dupadu Railway Station, NH-44, Lakshmipuram Post, Kurnool-51821891**Abstract:**

In an ideally regulated manufacturing industry, when a process is launched, its progress should be easily monitored and controlled until that process is completed. This means that at any given time, the condition and the quality of the product with respect to yield are transparent and known. This knowledge is lacking in current pharmaceutical manufacturing due to a lack of information feedback during the manufacturing process. This knowledge gap can be addressed by PAT solutions that report the condition of a product in real-time and facilitate the introduction of a feedback loop to control a process based on the reported parameters. Such an approach allows to test quality of the product at different manufacturing stages to ensure quality by design (QbD) from raw materials to intermediate, and to the final drug product.

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INTRODUCTION:

Process Analytical Technology (PAT) was defined by the Food and Drug Administration guidance “PAT- A Framework for Innovative Pharmaceutical Development, Manufacturing and Quality Assurance” as a mechanism to design, analyse, and control pharmaceutical manufacturing process through the measurement of Critical Process Parameters (CPP) with Critical Quality Attributes (CQA) of the product. This encourages building quality into the design of the product and promoting the development of PAT solutions to digitize and provide real-time control of various critical parameters that influence product output and quality. In other types of industries including gas, petroleum and food industries PAT solutions have been widely implemented in process design to streamline product output. PAT technologies such as near-infrared spectroscopy (NIR), a widely known method for its capacity for accurate process monitoring of complex matrices, has been established as a highly versatile technique with a well-established process monitoring track record in several processing industries, e.g., to determine fuel octane numbers and benzene levels in fuel. In the biopharmaceutical industry the nature of the products is usually quite dynamic and complex, therefore making it more challenging to implement the PAT solutions currently used in other industries. However, there is ample opportunity and demand to develop PAT solutions to streamline bioproducts in the pharmaceutical industry, and there has been a lot of development of PAT into bioproduct design over the recent years. Therefore, this review will discuss the applications of PAT solutions at different stages of the pharmaceutical manufacturing using vaccine production as an example, the advantages and challenges at present state, and the vision of the future development to meet the needs of adaptable and predictive generations of biopharmaceutical manufacturing plants. [1]

In an ideally regulated manufacturing industry, when a process is launched, its progress should be easily monitored and controlled until that process is completed. This means that at any given time, the

condition and the quality of the product with respect to yield are transparent and known. This knowledge is lacking in current pharmaceutical manufacturing due to a lack of information feedback during the manufacturing process. This knowledge gap can be addressed by PAT solutions that report the condition of a product in real-time and facilitate the introduction of a feedback loop to control a process based on the reported parameters. Such an approach allows to test quality of the product at different manufacturing stages to ensure quality by design (QbD) from raw materials to intermediate, and to the final drug product. [2]

PAT has developed a broad suite of tools, including analytical, chemical, physical, microbiological, and risk analysis. Currently, traditional PAT approaches including off-line and at-line analysis, are used to provide quantitative information about a process using analytical tools. However, for these measurements the process is sampled, and the sample is then transported to a lab for analysis, which in turn results in a delay between process sampling and the availability of the results [Fig. 1C, D]. At-line analysis has the benefit that the testing is not done as far from the process site, therefore the turnover rate to relay results is faster than off-line methods. However, the goal of PAT is to be able to streamline in-line and on-line PAT measurements, to provide real-time data to be able to monitor and better control a process. On-line monitoring can be done by continuously re-directing samples outside a process to be directly measured at the process site without interruption or manual sampling, whereas in-line monitoring is directly interfaced within the process to provide real-time continuous measurements. This can be done by looping the sampling from the reactor to a monitoring vessel [Fig. 1A], or by interfacing the process with the analytical instrument in the reactor vessel [Fig. 1B], to create a feedback loop to modify the process conditions based upon real-time analysis. Therefore, a lot of current work focuses on method development to create PAT solutions capable to measure data in real-time and aid both process control and product quality. [3]

Fig. 1. Various methods of implementing PAT tools into bioprocess monitoring. A) On-line analysis includes sample cycling from the process and measured using an analytical tool to provide real-time data B) In-line analysis implements the analytical tool in the bioprocess to provide data in real-time as the process is occurring. C) Off-line analysis requires sampling from the bioprocess and transporting it for manual measurement in a different laboratory (i.e. Quality Control). D) At-line analysis requires manual sampling from the bioprocess and measuring the sample next to the bioprocess site, to improve acquisition time for the results. Created with BioRender.com.

At-line PAT solutions have traditionally been simpler to implement because the technologies do not interfere in the process they are intended to monitor because samples are measured outside the process. Whereas the in-line and on-line PAT solutions have been harder to integrate due to contact with the product and thus product integrity has to be demonstrated in order to comply with quality requirements in a regulated industry. Further development of PAT technology allows the use of non-invasive in-line and on-line probes and sensors to monitor processes in-line, with a goal to implement real-time product release. Therefore, the definition of different types of PAT implementations can be misguided because the implementation within a process is not directly related to whether the technology is involved in the process, but rather how simultaneously a product can be monitored throughout production to accurately represent change over time. [4]

Once applied to bioprocesses, PAT solutions can increase process understanding and control, and mitigate the risk from substandard drug products for both manufacturers and patients. To optimize the benefits of PAT, the entire PAT framework must be considered and each of the elements of PAT must be carefully selected, including sensors, analytical technology, data analysis techniques, control strategies, and process optimization routines. In

recent years, the diversity of PAT solutions has increasingly grown. There are many PAT technologies at different stages of development: some are applicable for the early research setting, whereas others have ventured into the manufacturing realm. Although more examples of PAT solutions now exist in the pharmaceutical industry, the breadth of coverage is still not comparable to some other types of industries mentioned because of difficulty in process implementation.

Current choices for implementation of PAT instruments within the production process are determined by information that is already known about the process, the type of current test is being employed, and whether implementation of analytical techniques in real-time would improve process control or higher quality/yield of desired antigens. Certain off-line techniques e.g., immunochemical methods are not currently technically feasible to be implemented in-line or on-line. On the other hand, certain product attributes such as concentration of various compounds, pH, osmolarity, temperature, and conformation changes of protein antigens during absorption can be monitored using on-line and in-line tools. Thus, various phases of the production cycle have been shown to have improved process measurement, characterization, and control by using analytical PAT methods. [5]

Portable and in-line PAT tools have been implemented in various bioprocesses including raw material identification, fermentation processes and downstream filtration and absorption studies to provide more robust data, that may not be well characterized or monitored. Raw material identification and quality testing has been one of the most robustly utilized processes for analytical tools. Since, chemical matrices are usually simple, and chemical properties can be detected by analytical techniques such as NIR, MIR, FTIR, NMR, and Raman spectroscopy, the implementation of PAT tools for raw material identification have been robust. Determining the quality of raw ingredients is very important in final product quality and safety, and implementation of robust real-time methods for raw material identification can quality control, and process testing and validation. A few examples of techniques explored include non-destructive analytical PAT tools such as FTIR, Raman, and LD, which have been used in both off-line and in-line raw material identification of AlPO₄ adjuvant and its characterization during intermediate and final stages of production. Off-line sampling using an NIR probe during fermentation provided information about critical process parameters that could be further implemented in-line. Moreover, development using small scale studies have shown the efficacy of monitoring adjuvants, and absorption of antigens, and downstream filtration using both real-time and off-line PAT tools. Therefore, the focus is to develop and integrate real-time release of products by streamlining at-line, on-line or in-line PAT solutions, which will ultimately provide better control of the production of biologics throughout the manufacturing process.

Therefore, the major goals of PAT integration into the manufacturing process can be summarized as the following three: the reduction of product cycle times via real-time measurement and control systems; reduction of waste and reworks of final product; and the possibility for real-time product release. In this review our focus is on PAT applications for vaccines throughout various stages of manufacturing including upstream and downstream processes, formulation and filling of drug substance and drug product, and discussion of the challenges and successes, as well as future directions essential to succeed with digital evolution in pharmaceutical and vaccine industries. [6]

PAT IN PHARMACEUTICALS AND VACCINES:

Recently, development of PAT solutions for the monitoring of bioprocesses has been investigated to understand and control more complex and dynamic biological products such as vaccines. Vaccine technologies are complex and created with different bioprocesses. There are many different types of technological vaccine platforms including live attenuated pathogens, inactivated whole pathogens, toxoid antigens, or parts of pathogens including natural or recombinant proteins, conjugated or unconjugated polysaccharides, virus-like particles, or DNA/RNA vaccines. The development of each type of vaccine requires different biological systems and requirements. Therefore, PAT tools are being used to better understand and control different phases of the manufacturing lifecycle [Fig. 2].

Fig. 2. Process Analytical Technology (PAT) tools for Bioprocess monitoring throughout the Manufacturing Lifecycle. Schematic for the use of various analytical tools (i.e. Near-infrared spectroscopy (NIR), Mid-infrared spectroscopy (MIR), Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR), Raman Spectroscopy, and Differential Light Scattering (DLS)) for monitoring different types of biological products throughout upstream and downstream production processes. [7]

Although the manufacturing lifecycle is adapted for specific types of antigen production, the overall processes are similar, and include opportunities for various PAT tool applications during every phase [Fig. 2]. Upstream operations are defined by the processes involved in growth and cultivation of a desired antigen. The upstream lifecycle includes opportunities for process monitoring starting from raw material preparation throughout fermentation and cultivation of a desired antigen. Current development focuses on the implementation of on-line or in-line PAT solutions to provide information about critical process parameters that impact upstream fermentation in real-time. Downstream processes can also be monitored to assess antigen purity and formulation for the drug substance (i.e., adjuvant absorption) and final drug product (i.e., final vaccine product). [Fig. 2]. Furthermore, downstream PAT applications for real-time monitoring and process control are garnering

greater interest in PAT implementation to control processes that impact final products. Technological advancements in PAT that utilizes biochemical and biophysical analyses make it possible to monitor processes in-line and in real time often by probe insertion directly into the manufacturing line in reactors, connectors, and vessels. Thus, by developing PAT solutions to monitor various phases of the manufacturing lifecycle, it will help monitor product consistency to streamline the faster development of high quality and more affordable biological products. Therefore, the subsequent section will explore current development of various analytical PAT tools including NIR, IR, NMR, Raman, DLS, and particle count and imaging probes during various phases of the manufacturing lifecycle. [8]

Near-infrared spectroscopy (NIR):

NIR spectroscopy is a non-invasive analytical method that operates based on the principle that the atoms of molecules are in constant motion and vibrate at specific frequencies. The two main vibration types are stretching and bending, the type and frequency of each vibration are molecule specific and directly dependent upon the mass of each atom in the molecule and strength of the chemical bond between atoms. Light frequencies that correspond to molecular vibrations are absorbed by the sample and the resulting infrared spectrum (IR) comprises peaks of well-defined frequencies, band shapes and heights that can be correlated to molecule concentrations present in the sample. Theoretically, the concentration of any molecule containing C–H, N–H, S–H or O–H bonds can be measured. Compared to IR that detects fundamental vibrations, NIR measures higher energy wavelengths that create combination and overtone vibrations. Fundamental vibrations are defined as a transition of energy from the ground state to a first excited state. However, NIR vibrational frequencies comprise of combinations or overtones which are defined as excitations from the ground state to a level above the first excited state. Thus, an advantage of NIR is that it displays weak absorbance bands that return more signal to the detector. Since the weaker absorbance bands cause less specular reflectance, therefore samples do not require dilution to be measured. [9]

Although NIR is very sensitive, the analysis of the spectra could be complex. As most mixtures in fermentation contain a variety of different molecules, this results in overlapping overtones. Therefore, differences in peak intensities resulted from different variables are not easily determined from the spectra and require multivariate statistical models to extrapolate information about different parameters. Thus, calibration models are built for each process parameter and are then validated against a reference set. In recent years there has been a lot of progress for developing models and methods to measure fermentation both on-line and in-line to provide real time information to further understand and control upstream bioprocesses. Measurement of parameters such as glucose, ammonium, lactate, glutamate, optical density/biomass, glycerol, and pH, have been developed using NIR in a variety of different organisms and explored during manufacturing fermentation. The ability to measure these parameters in real-time help to better understand growth processes and fermentation dynamics to better control bioprocesses to produce optimized yields. Studies have shown statistical models developed for individual parameters based on reference methods, however, the emergence of

process control using batch consistency or optimal run calibrations have also further allowed the development of NIR models without the need for reference calibration methods. Thus, the use of either modelling methods can allow real-time decisions to be monitored and controlled in real-time and have allowed the rapid development and use of NIR spectroscopy in bioprocess monitoring. [10]

Infrared spectroscopy:

Infrared spectroscopy is a type of vibrational spectroscopy that measures the infrared region of the electromagnetic spectrum. Different areas of the spectrum are associated with different vibrational energies and measurement of the Mid-IR (MIR) region (400–4000 cm⁻¹) can collect a molecular fingerprint of a compound through the measurement of its fundamental vibrations. In contrast to NIR, the resulting MIR spectrum can directly assign and resolve molecular peaks associated to organic molecules and can be used as a direct measurement to assign components in a solution. Although one drawback of the technique was the interference of water to detect components of aqueous solutions, the development of fibre optic probes using attenuated total reflectance (ATR) and Fourier Transformation have helped make the method better suited for monitoring bioprocess solutions. Compared to NIR, the pathlength in ATR fibre optic probes are commonly much shorter and therefore are not commonly used to measure biomass, however many other metabolic components of biological solutions such as glucose, lactate, ethanol, methanol, and ammonia were measured using this technology. [11]

The implementation of IR using in-line and on-line studies have been developed in smaller scales to measure upstream bioprocess parameters including glucose, lipids, and proteins to provide real-time process information. Other studies have explored the use of in-line ATR-FTIR probes in small scale fermenters to measure media composition from biomass, which was possible, however current work has not been able to accurately correlate CPP parameters in culture fermentation media at that scale. However, the implementation of these probes in large scale bioreactors needs to be further explored as current probes are not robust enough to be implemented in large scale bioprocesses. Moreover, although IR probes have been used to measure critical process parameters in upstream bioprocesses such as fermentation, there is less information about its measurement and use in downstream processes. Recently work has been shown using an in-line ATR probe in a small-scale study to monitor the

composition of aluminium phosphate adjuvant throughout the manufacturing process, including raw material, intermediate products, and final adjuvant product, as well as its absorption to an antigen. In addition, IR can be used to measure process residuals in-line, e.g., surfactant concentration in viral vaccine product. This work further demonstrates the application and use of IR technology to monitor bioprocesses but also further shows its capability to be implemented in-line to provide real-time data throughout the production process. [12]

Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR):

NMR is a spectroscopic technique that utilizes magnetic fields to study atomic nuclei of a sample. Since this method provides information for each nucleus in the entirety of a sample and is directly proportional to the intensity of the signal measured, NMR can be used to provide information about the characterization, and quantification of a variety of different materials. Moreover, when utilized as a PAT technology, similar statistical methodology can be applied for the pattern recognition of complex processes derived from NMR data.

There has been previous work investigating upstream bioprocesses and metabolite products measured by NMR off-line. However, recent studies have shown that sampling differences might exist between off-line and on-line NMR measurements, depending on the type of information about a process that is necessary. During reactions, conditions including temperature, pressure, and sample mixing, can contribute to various physical and chemical modifications of reactions including changes in solubility (precipitation), sample evaporation, or production of chemical intermediates. Therefore, on-line measurements in real-time provide the most robust information about the true reaction process compared to off-line sampling. Furthermore, continuous monitoring for kinetic models is better measured on-line to have more relevant representation of the reaction. Currently, various flow tube designs have been implemented to allow on-line reaction monitoring for magnets of various sizes, with the capability of continuous or stop-flow designs from reaction vessels to collect sample information. Furthermore, flow NMR designed for larger superconducting magnets also allows sample acquisition into the spectrometer and accounts for various flow effects that are representative in the acquired data, without the need for instrument modification, and provides comprehensive data for measuring various chemical reactions. [13]

Although excellent methods have been developed for off-line and flow monitoring of bioprocesses using high-field NMR magnets, the implementation of these instruments in production has been challenging. However, in recent years low-field NMR spectrometers containing permanent magnets, that do not require the use of cryogenics, have been developed to monitor reaction processes because of the simple instrument maintenance and capability to provide real-time process information. These smaller “bench-top” NMR spectrometers helped to mitigate many of the issues with implementing high-field NMR spectrometers into production environments and can monitor processes in real-time using similar stop or continuous flow on-line reaction monitoring design systems. In-process sample testing using these bench-top NMR spectrometers are being developed, and studies done inside fume hoods in chemical industries demonstrated the feasibility of using these devices to monitor chemical reactions in real time. [14]

Apart from chemical reactions, there have been recent advancements of methods to monitor biologically relevant upstream fermentation processes using low-field NMR spectrometers. For example, recent studies have shown the capability of low-field NMR spectroscopy to monitor sucrose hydrolysis on-line. Furthermore, recent advances in bioprocess monitoring have shown improved methods of monitoring nutrient and metabolite profiles of both yeast and fungi and microalgae lipid profiles as well by on-line NMR using low-field NMR spectrometers. These developments can be applied to biopharmaceutical relevant processes, to monitor reaction progress in a robust way without the need to characterize various components individually. In downstream processes, the study of sedimentation of aluminium adjuvanted suspensions, and freezing variability have been investigated in order to find out more about production process that can affect final drug products in a non-invasive manner. For both studies low field NMR spectrometers were able to non-invasively determine differences in sedimentation characteristics of suspensions with aluminium adjuvants, as well as freezing variability between vials using the same type of NMR methodology. In addition, ^{27}Al and ^{31}P NMR methods have also been developed to quantitatively measure total aluminium and free unbound phosphate in adjuvanted vaccines that can be measured throughout different phases of production. These studies provide further information for downstream parameters involved in formulation and stability for vaccines and could be applied for reaction monitoring of adjuvanted drug substances on-line.

Since, NMR can provide robust and direct quantitative sample information, and can measure many nuclei (i.e. hydrogen, carbon, phosphorous, aluminium) it can be used for a variety of biopharmaceutical relevant processes and is unique among other analytical methods. Due to these unique advantages, NMR has been shown as a good on-line reference technique for chemical reaction progress monitoring for other analytical techniques including NIR. As a reference method, NMR can quantitatively show reaction intermediates that are not represented by other current off-line reference techniques. Thus, further development of NMR for on-line monitoring in biological processes could also be used as a quantitative and robust on-line reference method to support other analytical techniques. [15]

Raman spectroscopy:

Raman spectroscopy is a form of vibrational spectroscopy that can provide information about chemical properties and molecular interactions of various compounds, which in turn can provide a molecular fingerprint of any given compound. Raman active compounds are molecules that have changes in polarizability and result in the inelastic scattering of photons that produce vibrational energy from excitation by a laser. These vibrational modes are mapped and result in spectra that can provide both chemical and physical information about a sample of interest.

Over recent years advances in Raman spectrometers and analytical software have allowed for better spectral information and have made Raman a common analytical technique used in industry. One of the many reasons this technology has become more popular for industrial bioprocess monitoring is because Raman spectroscopy is rapid to implement, cost effective, non-destructive to samples, easily reproducible and can measure a variety of both organic and inorganic substrates. Raman can be implemented in-situ and has been implemented to provide consistent sample measurements for a variety of process that can include both liquids, solids, gases, and aerosols, making the technique very versatile. Due to the technique versatility, there has been a lot of studies showing the implementation and use of Raman spectroscopy in pharmaceutical industries to measure raw materials and various chemical progression steps including tablet mixing and drying. Further development of Raman spectroscopy for monitoring applications in biopharmaceutical industries has been adapted to provide real-time process information. [16]

Similarly, to NIR, the implementation of Raman probes on-line and in-line have provided the opportunity to obtain process information in real-time and have been coupled with chemometrics to provide robust information about a bioprocess. Studies have shown the development of models using in-line Raman probes to detect a variety of substrates important for fermentation and cell cultivation monitoring including glucose, glutamine, lactate, ammonia and glutamate in various types of cell systems. Moreover, Raman spectroscopy has been implemented as on-line PAT solutions in bioprocesses to monitor and control looped systems to measure metabolites and viable cell density which is important for fermentation. Furthermore, real-time just-in-time learning (RT-JITL) frameworks are under development to help maintain industrial Raman models that can be used for real-time fermentation monitoring. These developments further demonstrate the evolving use and benefit of implementing Raman PAT solutions for bioprocess control. Further development of amino acid monitoring in bioreactors in-real time using Raman spectroscopy has also been studied to provide further information about parameters that influence cell culture growth processes. These models can help provide real-time bioreactor monitoring for fermentation parameters that can affect the growth, expression, and selection of various cell systems to better control a process to produce a desired yield.

Furthermore, the ability to measure various components involved in the manufacturing process for vaccine development helps exemplify the versatility of using Raman in both upstream and downstream processes to provide a robust and singular method to identify and measure a variety of components important for vaccine development that can be further implemented in real-time. Raman spectroscopy has also been developed to measure variability between various vaccine products with similar antigens to assess quality and identity between batch releases and various products to ensure safety and quality of released biopharmaceuticals. Thus, further implementation of Raman spectroscopy in-line in these industries can help further develop analytical tools to provide real-time information about biological products during manufacturing processes. [17]

Dynamic light scattering (DLS):

Dynamic light scattering (DLS) is a technique that correlates the Brownian motion and resulting light scattering of particles in solution and is used to provide information about particle size and distribution. The technique has been widely developed

and used to measure a variety of different biological particles. DLS has been used to provide information about biological molecules with relevance to the production and understanding of biopharmaceuticals. A recent study used DLS to measure pre-absorbed antigens to examine consistency of antigen size distribution prior to association with adjuvants, and to further compare with the adsorbed state, i.e., the consistency of size of antigens associated adjuvants for the formulation of vaccine products measured by laser diffraction (LD) and in-line by Focused Beam Reflectance Measurement (FBRM). The application of DLS has also been developed to provide information about particle size and stability of a variety of pharmaceutically relevant proteins. Most recent studies have shown the use of DLS for monitoring the effect of temperature on SARS-CoV-2 spike and RBD proteins to determine the stability of the proteins after storage at 4 °C, by correlating their molecular weight.

Recently, the development of an on-line application of DLS capable to measure size distribution of protein antigens and oil-in-water adjuvants can provide real-time characterization and enable decisions to develop and optimize manufacturing processes. Statistical modelling using artificial neuronal networks (ANN) have been developed using DLS to measure average yeast cell size throughout stages of cell growth by monitoring the diameter of the cells. The development of this model in cell culture suspension can be used to further study the particle size of cells during upstream processes to provide information about cell growth. This could also be further applied to other organisms to provide another technique to measure applications of biomass which are currently not well characterized or understood. Another technique adaptable for the on-line application is real-time MALS, which in addition to size also reports molecular weight distribution. However, the PAT methods using DLS and MALS in bioprocess monitoring during manufacturing would need to be further developed for applicable real-time process control. [18]

Particle count and imaging probes:

Technological advancements in PAT that utilizes biochemical and biophysical analyses make it possible to monitor processes in-line and in real time often by probe insertion directly into the manufacturing line in reactors, connectors, and vessels. The implementation of PAT to monitor antigen adsorption may facilitate new product development and process optimization for commercialized products. Further process understanding as a whole, and reduce lost batches by

allowing for continuous monitoring and decision-making in real time. It will also accelerate and streamline testing processes by reducing downtime of waiting for test results to release a batch, and providing robust, continuous data collection. During development of formulations, it can be used in scaled-down models and then used to verify characteristics at full scale, simplifying and accelerating process definition.

Particle size is a quality attribute of adjuvanted vaccines that requires monitoring. During processing as large adjuvanted particles can potentially decrease potency of a vaccine. One of the methods that monitors the number, size, and shape of particles through chord length distribution is focused beam reflectance measurement (FBRM™). It was shown that Particle Track and Easy Viewer probes with iC FBRM™ and iC Vision™ software, respectively, detect differences between a normal adjuvanted formulation and one that contains aggregates. They are also able to detect subtle particle size distribution changes during the antigen adjuvant adsorption processes. Measurements were made using both the real-time probes and with off-line benchtop laser diffraction instrument as an orthogonal testing assay to understand similarities. In addition, in-line particle sizing by FBRM and mid IR probes were shown as useful tools for in-process characterization and identification of adsorbed vaccine drug product. [19]

In downstream formulation process, equipped with an imaging probe, FBRM can be used to monitor the loss of fine particles prior to filtration, which can markedly decrease the time needed for filtration. Other techniques employed include particle vision monitoring (PVM), which can be used to monitor the transition between oiling and crystallization. In 2005, Pfizer researchers considered the power of PAT to understand processes as self-evident and described usage of PAT for crystallizations on scale and redox reactions. There are success stories of PAT integration into manufacturing process of the pharmaceuticals especially for the manufacturing of solid formulations.

The use of real-time measurements for the exploration and manufacturing of new vaccines enables new efficient ways to gain initial understanding on the association of adjuvant with an antigen of interest. Currently, the utility of an adjuvant to a given vaccine antigen is determined on a case-by-case basis. By characterizing and trending the adsorption process in real time, PAT has the potential to dramatically reduce precious

investigation time required for next generation vaccine manufacturing by providing a mechanism of visualizing antigen-adjuvant complex chemical structure changes. This technology may also assist in selecting the most suitable adjuvant for the antigens being absorbed. Therefore, future regulatory support of PAT implementation for measuring drug substance and drug products, aims to integrate the use of these technologies in the next generation of vaccine manufacturing. [20]

PAT IN DIGITAL MANUFACTURING:

PAT is a portal to digital:

The significant impact of implementing analytical tools using PAT, is to create digitized processes with feedback loop control, to better understand, control and optimize bioprocesses. By understanding critical process parameters (CPPs) that influence bioprocesses, that knowledge can be adapted and optimized to use in various platforms. Thus, when generating large amounts of data, a virtual digital copy (i.e. Digital Twin) could be created to provide information about a process and expected data readout with associated software, to simulate a

manufacturing process, along to change and adapt equipment and procedures for a new platform. Thus, the digital copy containing all the critical information about a process can be transferred from various plants or physical locations to a new process. Ideally the creation of a digital twin blueprint to transfer technology, knowledge and analysis could be implemented to adapt current processes to development of various antigens without the need to begin validation and optimization of a bioprocess from scratch. Thus, digital twins can provide information about the process, i.e. digital blueprint, that would allow its quick shipment and adaptation in a novel environment [Fig. 3]. However, in the biopharmaceutical industry the development of digital twins is complex because of the dynamic nature of the products. Therefore, transfer of technology is not as easily implemented as in other industries (i.e. petrol and automotive industries) because knowledge about the various parameters that impact a process is not fully understood, or sometimes similar between platforms, therefore the development of a digital twin copy is inherently more complex.

Fig. 3. Schematic design for the implementation of a Digital Twin in the Biopharmaceutical industry. Physical processes and digital processes are combined to create digitized models and are developed using machine learning to better predict outcomes of important biological process parameters. Copies of these models are then implemented to

different products or sites to create templates with required parameters to measure and predict outputs of a new design. Created with BioRender.com.

Although digital twins are more complex to develop in biopharmaceuticals, there is a large opportunity to maximize operational gain in the industry. This includes the application of PAT solutions, to create more efficient processes with greater control and regulation, that can ultimately improve the quality of biological products. This can help provide solutions to decrease the cost of goods, development of new processes, improve product quality, and better satisfy requirements outlined by various regulators to help maximize operational gain and faster development and release of new biopharmaceuticals to the market. [21]

To date there are not any digital twins being directly applied in biopharmaceutical applications, there has been a lot of work in developing models to create digital twin frameworks that can be used for bioprocesses in biopharmaceutical manufacturing. There has been work mapping CHO cell culture kinetics using genetic modelling to predict metabolic changes in the cell platform. Since these cells are often used as platforms for growth of different recombinant proteins, these models can help to develop better metabolic monitoring strategies for digital twins using the CHO cell platform. Further work has also demonstrated the feasibility of using Raman spectroscopy and Diode array detector (DAD) as PAT methods to predict concentrations of mAb using a simulation study to determine process control prediction that could be applied to a future digital twin framework concept. Interestingly, a study outlining the prior use and of knowledge of various PAT bioprocess methods, have been integrated to propose a complete manufacturing digital twin framework for a production of a SARS-COVID-19 mRNA vaccine This framework could be further tested in a larger industrial scale to try and improve production understanding and scale-up timing for the manufacturing production of a COVID-19 vaccine to meet requirements. Thus, the importance of the development of digital twin frameworks in biopharmaceutical manufacturing is important in order to be able to quickly respond to consumer needs, while providing robust methods to monitor various production processes for different biological products, in order to achieve optimal product production and safety. [22]

PAT data analysis:

Since different types of analytical tools require different types of data processing, choosing an appropriate analytical method is important, so that it

is able to provide continuous process information about critical process parameters of interest, in a stable, linear, robust and repetitive manner Moreover, the type of modelling selected to incorporate empirical, data driven, and statistical approaches have been explored using PAT for Design of Experiments (DoE) and Hybrid modelling, that have been effective for process modelling using multivariate data analysis.

Technologies such as Mid-IR, require more simplistic univariate analysis, and can be used to provide information about analytes of interest using band height or area of peaks that directly correlate to chemical information of the modelling system. However, other technologies that provide secondary information about processes with many collinearities such as NIR, require multivariate modelling. Thus, the analytical method chosen, and appropriate data processing methods, will reflect the results of the entire process and determine if the method is able to provide sensitive and selective monitoring of analytes that fit within the model's scope of measurement under varying conditions that can be predictively replicated Thus, the robustness and reliability of measurement of critical process parameters relies on data analytics that are appropriately determined for each process and type of analytical sensor. [23]

Most commonly multivariate data analysis (MVDA) is necessary to reveal hidden patterns in data sets and interactions between parameters for methods that cannot provide direct chemical or physical information about processes MVDA analysis is employed when there is a large amount of data points that cannot be modelled individually and require the reduction of data in order to find useful information about all the variables The two most common types of MVDA data analysis employed during bioprocess monitoring is Principal component analysis (PCA) and Partial least square regression (PLS) .. Both types of analysis are sensitive to data pre-treatment or preprocessing methods which can help to reduce noise and find better information about process parameters based on their chemical and physical attributes that impact the spectral signal. There are various pre-treatments to normalize differences and scaling between parameters, and other pre-treatment methods to help correct baseline shifts which can help to reduce the impact of scattering and instrument drifts.

Once appropriate pre-processing treatments are employed to spectral data, models can be built to determine information about bioprocess data from the spectra. PCA analysis can provide qualitative information about data without requiring reference methods, and can monitor the structure, variance and distribution of data generated directly from measurements. Quantitative information about bioprocess parameters can also be determined using reference methods for model calibration determined by partial least square regressions (PLS). Both types of information can be very useful to monitor bioprocesses using PAT tools. Qualitative models can provide information about bioprocess progression, by comparing batch data to previous or ideal batch consistencies to provide information about the quality or performance of the process. Quantitative models can help provide information between process variables and data, to better monitor various parameters throughout the bioprocess and provide further understanding of the process. Both methods require robust calibration models to be created, and validated using new data sets, in order to ensure predictability of the model and robustness, in order to account for drifts and changes throughout the data and process parameters changes due to the dynamic nature of bioprocesses and materials used. Therefore, model maintenance is important to account for differences in starting material and changes in the system over time. Guidance for MVDA modelling and how they can be applied for bioprocesses is outlined in USP chapter 1039 and provides excellent framework to design chemometric models based on regulatory guidance. In order to design implement MVDA modelling into manufacturing infrastructures, there are IT programs available that meet 21 CFR part 11 compatibility that streamline data from analytical instruments and are able to process and visualize MVDA data. IT Programs such as Sint, SIPAT, Bio PAT SIMCA and Unscrambler Process Pulse II are commercially available programs to streamline various analytical instruments and associated data. Thus, implementation of these programs can help standardize data collection and analysis for various PAT instruments for use in industrial environments.

The use of data driven models can be further applied using machine learning in biopharmaceutical manufacturing. However, the challenge with implementing PAT models using machine learning into the manufacturing suites is to demonstrate the robustness of the models for GMP use, and ensure the compliance regulatory requirements. Li et al., describe an framework called a stage-gate model, to provide guidance for PAT progression to design and

implement PAT technologies into biomanufacturing processes while maintaining GMP practices and strict regulatory requirements. Part of the framework that Li et al. describe is the necessity to define the robustness of the technology that is planned to be implemented in a real time process and determine its comparability to previously established methods so that it is equally compared to historical data to provide valid results. Moreover, process design and understanding of the stringent parameters of a specific part of the process is also important in determining which technologies to implement and what kind of variability in the model is acceptable to produce accurate results and quality data. [24]

This provides a challenge when implementing machine learning models into bioprocesses because the processes are often quite complex and variable in nature so proper training and use of various types of modelling may be required to provide understanding of parameter limits that are acceptable. Then, machine learning in the context of bioprocess monitoring can be applied to systems in the digital realm to predict the response on changing conditions and control the process without the continuous addition of empirical data, relying on MVDA models created for critical process parameters. To date there have been improvements in implementing machine learning to predict bioprocess monitoring. Off-line metabolic analysis using CHO cells were adapted using machine learning to provide better prediction of amino acid concentration throughout a bioprocess, which can be adapting into production to control nutrient feeding and potentially be further built using in-line PAT technologies [81]. Further work has shown implementation of real-time machine learning algorithms to predict various parameters in cell culturing monitoring that adapt a specific model in-real time to provide better prediction and control of the process from the model with the lowest prediction error.]. The implementation of machine learning for model maintenance shown for Raman models measuring metabolites in bioprocesses, is an example of how these systems could be implemented in manufacturing suites to maintain accuracy of models to satisfy strict quality regulations. Thus, models such as these can be further implemented in complex processes with various process parameters throughout the production process to implement machine learning algorithms to provide better forecasting and control, that can maintain valid prediction limits to fit regulatory requirements compared to current models. This helps advance the ultimate goal to predict product outcome over a variety of processes in the manufacturing plant generation 4.0, to drastically

reduce downtime and allow for a remote workforce, and promote optimal quality for real-time release products. [25]

Decisions in real time – compression of time for faster product development:

The necessity of developing and implementing PAT into bioprocesses is instrumental to control and understand biological product development in real-time. This will provide insight into processes throughout the manufacturing lifecycle, and how various process parameters can impact final vaccine antigen or biological product yield and quality. Moreover, real-time monitoring of bioprocesses can help apply critical parameters commonly used amongst various product platforms to adapt to new bioprocesses and develop in-line monitoring of new antigens. The importance of being able to quickly transfer real-time process monitoring and knowledge to new antigens or platforms is important for faster development and scale-up for new projects that are important for industrial and consumer needs. This can be exemplified in recent applications seen, due to the need of rapid vaccine development in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. The consequences of the pandemic helped biopharmaceutical industries to understand the necessity of innovation in process understanding and control, and its importance to competitively create and understand new biological products and scale-up for quick development and validation of both upstream and downstream processes to develop biological products in response to medical need. [27]

PAT methods developed to date could be further improved and tested for robustness to begin implementation in real bioprocess production suites to ensure stable and accurate models that will satisfy regulatory requirements. To integrate these PAT tools throughout various manufacturing processes, the focus of future development should also adapt current PAT technologies using single-use bioreactor systems. Thus, by adapting current technologies and implementing them in adaptable single-use formats, real production data can be further collected to provide more information about full scale manufacturing and help build robust process models. Moreover, the development of single use sensors and bioreactor systems will help the industry to comply with strict regulatory requirements involved in production and will help promote agile development of new models for various bioproduct platforms.. This ultimately could help implementation of these technologies into current and future manufacturing spaces, while reducing lead time to develop PAT methods for

automated real-time release products. Therefore, the implementation of PAT tools in the biopharmaceutical industry should be further developed to provide better understanding of complex biological processes, to create better streamlined and digitized manufacturing processes for future biological products. [28]

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Conflicts of Interest:

Gabriella Gerzon and Yi Sheng are employees of York University, and Marina Kirkitadze is an employee of Sanofi Pasteur. The authors have no relevant affiliations or financial involvement with any organization or entity with a financial interest in or financial conflict with the subject matter or materials discussed in the manuscript.

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